

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Supplementary information for

The simulation and analysis of on-farm trials data using linear mixed models in SAS and CRAN R environments, when the factors involved consist of both fixed and random levels.

Supplementary Boxes

Supplementary Box 1: Data Layout for a One-factor Example in SAS

```
data Data1;
input Obs factor$ rep$ group$ switch Y;
datalines;
  1       $r_{a1}$    1      random  1      5.4262
  2       $r_{a1}$    2      random  1      6.3829
  3       $r_{a1}$    3      random  1      6.1152
  4       $r_{a2}$    1      random  1      5.4659
  5       $r_{a2}$    2      random  1      5.6665
  6       $r_{a2}$    3      random  1      5.2195
  :      :       :       :       :       :
  N-2     $f_{a6}$    1      A6      0      6.0539
  N-1     $f_{a6}$    2      A6      0      5.8140
  N       $f_{a6}$    3      A6      0      5.7621
;
Proc print data= Data1;
```

Supplementary Box 2(a): Fitting a Single-factor Full Model in SAS

```
** Single-factor Full Model **;
proc glimmix data=Data1 outdesign=XZ;
class factor group rep;
model yield= group /ddfm=satterthwaite;
random group*factor*switch /v;
lsmeans group / lines;
Title "Single-factor Full Model";
run;
```

Supplementary Box 2(b): Fitting a Single-factor Full Model in R

```
## Single-factor Full Model

# Load necessary libraries:
library(lme4)      # for linear mixed models
```

```

# Fit a Two-factor full-factorial Model in R

# Defining the 'group' and 'switch' variables:
Data1$group <- as.factor(Data1$group)
Data1$switch <- as.numeric(Data1$switch)

# Fit the mixed-effects model
# Fit the linear mixed model:
model <- lmer(yield ~ group +
              (1 | group:factor:switch),
              data = Data1, REML = TRUE)
summary(model, ddf = "Kenward-Roger")

```

Supplementary Box 3: Data Layout for the CRD Example

```

data Data2;
input Obs factorA$ factorB$ rep$ Y;
datalines;
1      ra1    rb1    1      5.4262
2      ra1    rb1    2      6.3829
3      ra1    rb1    3      6.1152
4      ra1    rb1    4      5.4659
5      ra1    rb1    5      5.6665
6      ra2    rb1    1      5.2195
7      ra2    rb1    2      5.5668
:
:
N      fa6    fb7    5      5.7621
;
Proc print data= Data2;

```

Supplementary Box 4(a): Generating the 'Group' and 'Switch' Variables in SAS

```

/* Creating 'group' and 'switch' variables for the factor levels*/
/* For example, let factorA = A, groupA = gA, and switchA = sA */

data Data2groups;
set Data2;
rename FactorA = A
       FactorB = B;
Proc print data= Data2groups (obs=10);
run;

data Data2groups;
set Data2groups;
if A = 'A5' then gA='A5';

```

```

ELSE if A ='A6' then gA='A6';
else gA='random';

if gA ='A5' then sA=0;
ELSE if gA='A6' then sA=0;
else sA=1;

if B ='B4' then gB='B4';
ELSE if B ='B6' then gB='B6';
ELSE if B ='B7' then gB='B7';
else gB='random';

if gB='B4' then sB=0;
ELSE if gB='B6' then sB=0;
ELSE if gB='B7' then sB=0;
else sB=1;
run;
proc print data=Data2groups (obs=50); /* view first 50 rows */
run;

```

Supplementary Box 4(b): Generating the ‘*Group*’ and ‘*Switch*’ Variables in R

```

## Rename dataset
Data2 <- simulated_data
head(Data2)

library(dplyr)
Data2 <- Data2 %>%
  rename(
    A=FactorA,
    B=FactorB
  )
head(Data2)

## Creating "group" and "switch" variables (groupA = gA, and
switchA = sA)
library(dplyr)
Data2groups <- Data2 %>%

mutate(gA = case_when(A == 'A5' ~ 'A5',
                      A == "A6" ~ "A6",
                      TRUE ~ "random"),
sA = as.numeric(gA == "random"),

gB = case_when(B == "B4" ~ "B4",
               B == "B6" ~ "B6",

```

```

        B == "B7" ~ "B7",
        TRUE ~ "random"),
    sB = as.numeric(gB == "random")
)
head(Data2groups) # A tibble dataset
Data2groups<-as.data.frame(Data2groups) # rename and convert
tibble to dataframe
head(Data2groups, 20) # view first 20 rows

```

Supplementary Box 5(a): Fitting a two-factor full-factorial model in SAS

```

/* Fit the two-factor full model */
proc glimmix data= Data2groups outdesign=XZ ;
class A B gA gB;
model yield= gA|gB / ddfm=kr solution;
random gA*A*sA
        gA*gB*B*sB
        gB*B*sB
        gB*gA*A*sA
        gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB;
covtest / wald;
/* Pairwise contrasts between the three levels of factor A */
lsmeans gA / pdiff=all cl; /* All pairwise comparisons of factor A
levels with confidence limits */
lsmeans gB / pdiff=all cl; /* All pairwise comparisons of factor B
levels with confidence limits */

Title "Two-factor Full-factorial Model";
run;

```

Supplementary Box 5(b): Fitting a two-factor full-factorial model in R

```

# Load necessary libraries:
library(lme4) # for linear mixed models
library(lmerTest) # for TYPE III tests, ddfm = "Kenward-Roger"
library(emmeans) # LS-means
library(multcomp) # cld() for emmeans
library(multcompView) # Optional low-level CLDs
library(ggplot2) # Plotting
library(dplyr) # Data handling

# Fit a two-factor full-factorial model:
Full.model2 <- lmer(
yield ~ gA * gB +
(sA-1 | gA:A) +
(sB-1 | gA:gB:B) +
(sB-1 | gB:B) +
(sA-1 | gB:gA:A) +

```

```

      (sA:sB-1 | gA:A:gB:B),
      data = Data2groups
    )
summary(Full.model2, ddf = "Kenward-Roger") # fixed effects
cat("\n=== Type III F-tests ===\n")
print(anova(Full.model2, ddf = "Kenward-Roger"))

```

Supplementary Box 6(a): Generating Marginal Means with Pairwise Comparisons and Letter Display in SAS

```

** First submit/run the %mult macro code here once **;

/*The Barley Example - Marginal means for non-significant
interaction effects*/
proc glimmix data= Data2groups ;
class A B gA gB;
model yield= gA|gB /ddfm=kr solution ;
random gA*A*sA
      gA*gB*B*sB
      gB*B*sB
      gB*gA*A*sA
      gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB;
      covtest / wald;
** Slice by groupA and generate LSmeans **;
lsmeans gA*gB/ diff adjust=tukey lines;
slice gA*gB/sliceby=gA lines;

** Slice by groupB and generate LSmeans **;
lsmeans gA*gB/ diff adjust=tukey lines;
slice gA*gB/sliceby=gB lines;

** Optional: Interaction means (if gA*gB is significant or of
interest) **;
lsmeans gA*gB / pdiff=all cl slice=gA;
run;

/*The Barley Example - %MULT macro with proc glimmix */
proc glimmix data=Data2groups;
ods output lsmeans=lsmeans diffs=diffs;
class A B gA gB;
model yield= gA|gB /ddfm=kr solution ;
random gA*A*sA
      gA*gB*B*sB
      gB*B*sB
      gB*gA*A*sA
      gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB;
      covtest / wald;

```

```

/* Adjust for multiple comparisons (optional if using %mult macro)
*/
lsmeans gA*gB/pdiff;
%mult(trt=gA, by=gB);
%mult(trt=gB, by=gA);
run;

```

Supplementary Box 6(b): Generating Marginal Means with Pairwise Comparisons and Letter Display in R

```

## Letter Display and Marginal Means for the Two-factor full-factorial Model:

# -----
### Pairwise comparisons like LSMeans
# -----

library(emmeans) # for lsmeans and pairwise comparisons
emmeans(Full.model2, pairwise ~ gA, adjust = "none") # or adjust
= "none" to match SAS pdiff=all

## SLICING & LETTER DISPLAY

# -----
### Optional: SAS-like contrasts
# -----

options(contrasts = c("contr.sum", "contr.poly"))

# -----
# LS-means and Pairwise comparisons of gB sliced by gA
# -----

emm <- emmeans(Full.model2, ~ gB | gA)
pairs_emm <- contrast(emm, method = "pairwise", adjust = "none")
cat("\n=== Pairwise Comparisons ===\n")
print(summary(pairs_emm))

# -----
### CLD: Letters (Unadjusted) sliced by gA
# -----

cld_results <- cld(emmeans(Full.model2, ~ gB | gA), adjust =
"none", Letters = letters)
# Convert to data frame
cld_table <- as.data.frame(cld_results)
# Rename grouping column (if needed)
if (".group" %in% names(cld_table)) {

```

```

cld_table <- cld_table %>% rename(Letters = .group)
}

# Print the final table
cat("\n=== LS-means of gB sliced by gA (Unadjusted) ===\n")
print(cld_table)

# -----
### Plot: LS-means of gB with Letters
# -----

ggplot(cld_table, aes(x = gB, y = emmean, color = gA)) +
  geom_point(position = position_dodge(0.4), size = 3) +
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = lower.CL, ymax = upper.CL),
               width = 0.2, position = position_dodge(0.4)) +
  geom_text(aes(label = Letters),
            position = position_dodge(0.4), vjust = -1.2, size =
5) +
  labs(
    title = "LS-means of gB sliced by gA (Unadjusted Letter
Display)",
    x = "gB", y = "Estimated Mean Yield"
  ) +
  theme_minimal()

# -----
### LS-means of gA sliced by gB
# -----

cld_gA_by_gB <- cld(emmeans(Full.model2, ~ gA | gB), adjust =
"none", Letters = letters)

# Convert and clean up
cld_table <- as.data.frame(cld_gA_by_gB)
if (".group" %in% names(cld_table)) {
  cld_table <- cld_table %>% rename(Letters = .group)
}

# Print CLD table
cat("\n=== LS-means of gA sliced by gB (Unadjusted CLD) ===\n")
print(cld_table)

# -----
### Plot: LS-means of gA sliced by gB
# -----

ggplot(cld_table, aes(x = gA, y = emmean, color = gB)) +

```

```

geom_point(position = position_dodge(0.4), size = 3) +
geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = lower.CL, ymax = upper.CL),
              width = 0.2, position = position_dodge(0.4)) +
geom_text(aes(label = Letters),
          position = position_dodge(0.4), vjust = -1.2, size =
5) +
labs(
  title = "LS-means of gA sliced by gB (Unadjusted Letter
Display)",
  x = "gA", y = "Estimated Mean Yield"
) +
theme_minimal()

# -----
### Generate SED, LSD, and HSD for groupA
# -----

# Generate estimated marginal means for groupA sliced by groupB
emm_groupA <- emmeans(Full.model2, ~ gA | gB)

# Pairwise comparisons for groupA within each level of groupB
pairwise_sliced <- pairs(emm_groupA, adjust = "none")

# Specify the groupB slice of interest, e.g., groupB = "B4"
groupB_level <- "B4"

# Filter pairwise comparisons for groupB = "B4"
filtered_contrasts <- subset(as.data.frame(pairwise_sliced),
                             gB == "B4")

# Check if contrasts for groupB = "B4" exist
if (nrow(filtered_contrasts) > 0) {
  # Extract SED (Standard Error of Difference)
  sed_B4 <- filtered_contrasts$SE

  # Calculate LSD for groupB = "B4"
  alpha <- 0.05
  t_critical_B4 <- qt(1 - alpha / 2,
                    df = filtered_contrasts$df[1]) # Two-tailed
test
  lsd_B4 <- t_critical_B4 * sed_B4

  # Calculate HSD for groupB = "B4"
  q_critical_B4 <- qtkey(1 - alpha,
                        nmeans =
length(levels(recover_data(Full.model2)$gA)),
                        df = filtered_contrasts$df[1])
  hsd_B4 <- q_critical_B4 * sed_B4

```

```

# Create a table for SED, LSD, and HSD for groupB = "B4"
summary_table_B4 <- data.frame(
  Variable = c("SED", "LSD", "HSD"),
  Minimum = c(min(sed_B4), min(lsd_B4), min(hsd_B4)),
  Mean = c(mean(sed_B4), mean(lsd_B4), mean(hsd_B4)),
  Maximum = c(max(sed_B4), max(lsd_B4), max(hsd_B4))
)

# Print results
cat("\nSummary Statistics for SED, LSD, and HSD (gB = 'B4'):\n")
print(summary_table_B4)
} else {
  cat("\nNo pairwise comparisons found for gB = 'B4'.\n")
}

```

Supplementary Box 7: NDVI Data Layout for Repeated-Measures Design in SAS

```

data NDVI_univ;

input Obs FactorA FactorB Replication Yield Time;
datalines;
1      ra1    rb1    1      0.5320  1
2      ra1    rb1    2      0.6695  1
3      ra1    rb1    3      0.7784  1
4      ra1    rb1    4      0.6966  1
5      ra1    rb1    5      0.5122  1
6      ra1    rb1    6      0.3340  1
:      :      :      :      :      :

24     ra1    rb1    6      0.6944  4
25     ra1    rb2    1      0.5925  1
26     ra1    rb2    2      0.7484  1
:      :      :      :      :      :
1008   fa6    fb7    6      0.8107  4
;
Proc print data= NDVI_univ; /* Dataset in Univariate format */
Run;

```

Supplementary Box 8(a): SAS Code for Creating New Variables

```

/* Rename treatment factors */
data NDVI_groups;

```

```

set NDVIdata;
rename factorA = A
      factorB = B;

Proc print data=NDVI_groups (obs=10);
run;

/* Creating the 'group' and 'switch' variables in Lentils Data */
/* For example, let factorA = A, groupA = gA, and switchA = sA */

data NDVI_groups;
set NDVI_groups;
if A = 'A5' then gA = 'A5';
ELSE if A = 'A6' then gA = 'A6';
else gA = 'random';

if gA= 'A5' then sA =0;
ELSE if gA= 'A6' then sA =0;
else sA=1;

if B= 'B4' then gB='B4';
ELSE if B= 'B6' then gB='B6';
ELSE if B= 'B7' then gB='B7';
else gB='random';

if gB='B4' then sB=0;
ELSE if gB='B6' then sB=0;
ELSE if gB='B7' then sB=0;
else sB=1;
run;
proc print data=NDVI_groups (obs=10);
run;

```

Supplementary Box 8(b): R Code for Creating New Variables

```

## Rename variables
library(dplyr)

NDVI_groups <- NDVIdata %>%
  rename(
    A = FactorA,
    B = FactorB,
    rep = Rep
  )
head(NDVI_groups)

## Create 'Group' and 'Switch' variables
NDVI_groups <- NDVI_groups %>%

```

```

mutate(
  gA = case_when(
    A == "A5" ~ "A5",
    A == "A6" ~ "A6",
    TRUE ~ "random"),
  sA = as.numeric(gA == "random"),

  gB = case_when(
    B == "B4" ~ "B4",
    B == "B6" ~ "B6",
    B == "B7" ~ "B7",
    TRUE ~ "random" ),
  sB = as.numeric(gB == "random"),
)

# View the updated data
print(NDVI_groups)

```

Supplementary Box 9(a): SAS code for Plotting Mean NDVI by Factor B over time

```

/* Subset fixed levels of Factor B from NDVI Univariate Data */

Data FB_NDVI;
set NDVI_groups ;

where B in('B4','B6', 'B7' ) ;
run;
Proc print data=FB_NDVI (obs=10);
run;

/* Compute the mean NDVI contributed by Factor B*/
proc means noprint data= FB_NDVI nway;
var NDVI;
class A B rep Time;
output out=avg mean=avgNDVI;
run; /* new data set called avg created */

/* Plot NDVI by predictor FactorB over Time */
Proc gplot data=avg;
plot avgNDVI*Time= B / haxis=1 to 4 by 1 hminor=0 vminor=0;
symbol1 v=star c=BLUE i=join l=1;
symbol2 v=dot c=red i=join l=2;
symbol3 v=dot c=GREEN i=join l=3;
Symbol4 v=dot c=BLACK i=join l=4;
title "Mean NDVI per Time per Fixed Levels of FactorB";
run;
Quit;

```

Supplementary Box 9(b): R code for Plotting Mean NDVI by Factor B over time

```
# Subset fixed levels of Factor B from NDVI Univariate Data

library(dplyr)
FB_NDVI <- NDVI_groups %>%
  filter(B %in% c('B4', 'B6', 'B7'))

# View the subset data
print(FB_NDVI)

# Compute the mean NDVI contributed by Factor B
avg_NDVI <- FB_NDVI %>%
  group_by(A, B, rep, Time) %>%
  summarize(avgNDVI = mean(NDVI, na.rm = TRUE), .groups = 'drop')

# View the average data
print(avg_NDVI)

# Plot mean NDVI per Time for Factor B
ggplot(avg_NDVI, aes(x = Time, y = avgNDVI, color = B, shape = B,
group = B)) +
  geom_line(linewidth = 1) + # use 'linewidth' instead of 'size'
for ggplot2 >= 3.4
  geom_point(size = 2) +
  labs(title = "Mean NDVI per Time per Fixed Levels of FactorB",
x = "Time", y = "Mean NDVI") +
  scale_color_manual(values = c("blue", "red", "green")) +
  theme_minimal() +
  theme(legend.title = element_blank())
```

Supplementary Box 10(a): SAS PROC GLIMMIX code using SLICE or %MULT macro for the three-factor repeated-measures experiment.

```
** First submit/run the %mult code here once **;

/*The NDVI Groups Example - SLICE with GLIMMIX */
proc glimmix data=NDVI_groups ;
class A B Time gA gB rep;
model NDVI= gA|gB|Time /solution ddfm=kr;
random gA*A*sA
gA*gB*B*sB
```

```

gB*B*sB
gB*gA*A*sA
gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB
Time*gA*A*sA
Time*gA*gB*B*sB
Time*gB*B*sB
Time*gB*gA*A*sA
Time*gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB;
random Time /subject=rep*A*B type=ar(1);
covtest / wald;
lsmeans gA*Time / pdiff;
lsmeans gB*Time / pdiff;
slice gA*Time / sliceby=Time lines;
slice gB*Time / sliceby=Time lines;
run;

/*The NDVI Groups Example - %MULT with GLIMMIX */
proc glimmix data=NDVI_groups ;
ods output lsmeans=lsmeans diffs=diffs;
class A B Time gA gB rep;
model NDVI= gA|gB|Time /solution ddfm=kr;
random gA*A*sA
gA*gB*B*sB
gB*B*sB
gB*gA*A*sA
gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB
Time*gA*A*sA
Time*gA*gB*B*sB
Time*gB*B*sB
Time*gB*gA*A*sA
Time*gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB;
random Time/subject=rep*A*B type=ar(1);
covtest / wald;

/* All pairwise comparisons with confidence limits */

lsmeans gA*gB*Time/pdiff;
%mult(trt=gA, by=Time);
%mult(trt=gB, by=Time);
run;

```

Supplementary Box 10(b): R code for slicing and letter display for the three-factor repeated-measures experiment.

```

# Load necessary libraries
library(emmeans)      # LS-means
library(multcomp)     # cld() for emmeans
library(multcompView) # Optional low-level CLDs

```

```

library(ggplot2)      # Plotting
library(dplyr)        # Data handling

# Ensure Time and grouping variables are factors
# and switch variables are numeric
NDVI_groups <- NDVI_groups |>
  transform(
    gA  = factor(gA),
    gB  = factor(gB),
    A   = factor(A),
    B   = factor(B),
    sA  = as.numeric(sA), # changed from factor to numeric
    sB  = as.numeric(sB), # changed from factor to numeric
    rep = factor(rep),
    Time = factor(Time)   # crucial for time-dependent
    structures like AR(1)
  )

# Fit the model with AR(1) correlation structure
library(glmmTMB)

# Ensure Time is a factor
NDVI_groups$Time <- as.factor(NDVI_groups$Time)

# Fit the model
model <- glmmTMB(
  NDVI ~ gA * gB * Time +
    (1 | gA:A:sA) +
    (1 | gA:gB:B:sB) +
    (1 | gB:B:sB) +
    (1 | gB:gA:A:sA) +
    (1 | gA:A:sA:gB:B:sB) +
    (1 | Time:gA:A:sA) +
    (1 | Time:gA:gB:B:sB) +
    (1 | Time:gB:B:sB) +
    (1 | Time:gB:gA:A:sA) +
    (1 | Time:gA:A:sA:gB:B:sB) +
    ar1(Time + 0 | rep:A:B),
  family = gaussian,
  REML = TRUE,
  # Remove dispformula = ~0, to include the nugget variance
  start = list(theta = c(
    rep(log(0.001), 10), # Starting values for random effects (0.1,
0.001)
    log(0.1),           # Starting variance for AR(1)
    0                   # Starting correlation (AR parameter)
  )),
  data = NDVI_groups,
  control = glmmTMBControl(

```

```

    optArgs = list(method = "nlminb") # Alternative: method =
"BFGS"
  )
)

summary(model) # model does converges at SD = exp(-6.91) for the
RE's, SD = exp(-2.30) for AR(1), and 0 correlation.

#-----
### LSMeans (estimated marginal means) groupB sliced by Time
#-----

emm_gB_Time <- emmeans(model, ~ gB | Time)
contrast(emm_gB_Time, method = "pairwise")

#-----
### Generate CLD: Letters gB sliced by gA:
#-----

cld_results <- cld(emmeans(model, ~ gB | Time),
                  adjust = "none", Letters = letters)
# Convert to data frame
cld_table <- as.data.frame(cld_results)
# Rename grouping column (if needed)
if (".group" %in% names(cld_table)) {
  cld_table <- cld_table %>% rename(Letters = .group)
}

# Print the final table
cat("\n=== LS-means of gB sliced by Time ===\n")
print(cld_table)

#-----
### Plot: LS-means of gB with Letters
#-----

ggplot(cld_table, aes(x = gB, y = emmean, color = Time)) +
  geom_point(position = position_dodge(0.4), size = 3) +
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = lower.CL, ymax = upper.CL),
               width = 0.2, position = position_dodge(0.4)) +
  geom_text(aes(label = Letters),
            position = position_dodge(0.4), vjust = -1.2,
            size = 5) +
  labs(
    title = "LS-means of gB sliced by Time (Letter Grouping)",
    x = "gB", y = "Estimated Mean NDVI"
  )

```

```

) +
theme_minimal()

#-----
### LS-means and Pairwise comparisons of gA sliced by Time
#-----

emm <- emmeans(model, ~ gA | Time)
pairs_emm <- contrast(emm, method = "pairwise",
                      adjust = "none")
cat("\n=== Pairwise Comparisons ===\n")
print(summary(pairs_emm))

#-----
### Generate CLD: Letters gB sliced by gA:
#-----

cld_results <- cld(emmeans(model, ~ gA | Time),
                  adjust = "none", Letters = letters)
# Convert to data frame
cld_table <- as.data.frame(cld_results)
# Rename grouping column (if needed)
if (".group" %in% names(cld_table)) {
  cld_table <- cld_table %>% rename(Letters = .group)
}

# Print the final table
cat("\n=== LS-means of gA sliced by Time ===\n")
print(cld_table)

#-----
### Plot: LS-means of gB with Letters
#-----

ggplot(cld_table, aes(x = gA, y = emmean, color = Time)) +
  geom_point(position = position_dodge(0.4), size = 3) +
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = lower.CL, ymax = upper.CL),
               width = 0.2, position = position_dodge(0.4)) +
  geom_text(aes(label = Letters),
            position = position_dodge(0.4), vjust = -1.2,
            size = 5) +
  labs(
    title = "LS-means of gA sliced by Time (Letter Grouping)",
    x = "gB", y = "Estimated Mean NDVI"
  ) +

```

```
theme_minimal()
```

Supplementary Box 11(a): SAS Code for Split-split-plot Full Factorial Model

```
*** Creating the 'group' and 'switch' variables ***;
/* For example, let factorA = A, groupA = gA, and switchA= sA */
data Wheat_groups;
set Wheatdata;

rename factorA = A
       factorB = B
       factorC = C;
Proc print data=Wheat_groups (obs=20);
run;

data Wheat_groups;
set Wheat_groups;

if A = 'A2' then gA='A2';
ELSE if A = 'A4' then gA='A4';
else gA='random';

if gA = 'A2' then sA=0;
ELSE if gA='A4' then sA=0;
else sA=1;

if B = 'B2' then gB='B2';
ELSE if B = 'B4' then gB='B4';
ELSE if B = 'B6' then gB='B6';
ELSE if B = 'B8' then gB='B8';
else gB='random';

if gB = 'B2' then sB=0;
ELSE if gB='B4' then sB=0;
ELSE if gB='B6' then sB=0;
ELSE if gB='B8' then sB=0;
else sB=1;

if C = 'C1' then gC='C1';
ELSE if C = 'C2' then gC='C2';
ELSE if C = 'C3' then gC='C3';
else gC='random';

if gC = 'C1' then sC=0;
ELSE if gC='C2' then sC=0;
ELSE if gC='C3' then sC=0;
else sC=1;
```

```

proc print data= Wheat_groups;
run;

/* Fool-proof derivation of all effects in our three-way model.
   Each effect is formed by "termA.termB.termC". The first term
   corresponds to general intercept and can be ignored, as this
   term is fitted by default*/

data Effects;
do termA="          ", "gA", "gA.A.sA";
do termB="          ", "gB", "gB.B.sB";
do termC="          ", "gC", "gC.C.sC";
   output;
end;
end;
end;
run;

proc print data=Effects;
run;

** Full factorial Split-split-plot Model **;

/*Define the switch variables as numeric first, see Box 5 */
proc glimmix data=Wheat_groups outdesign=XZ ;
class A B C gA gB gC rep;
model yield= gA|gB|gC / ddfm=kr solution;
random rep(A);
random rep(A*B);
random gA*A*sA
      gA*A*sA*gB
      gB*B*sB
      gA*gB*B*sB
      gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB
      gA*A*sA*gC
      gA*A*sA*gB*gC
      gB*B*sB*gC
      gA*gB*B*sB*gC
      gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB*gC
      gC*C*sC
      gA*gC*C*sC
      gA*A*sA*gC*C*sC
      gB*gC*C*sC
      gA*gB*gC*C*sC
      gA*A*sA*gB*gC*C*sC
      gB*B*sB*gC*C*sC
      gA*gB*B*sB*gC*C*sC

```

```
gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB*gC*C*sC;
Title "Three-factor Split-split-plot full Model ";
run;
```

Supplementary Box 11(b): R Code for Split-split-plot Full Factorial Model

```
library(tidyverse)
library(lme4)

# Creating the 'group' and 'switch' variables

Wheat_groups <- Wheatdata %>%
  rename(
    A = factorA,
    B = factorB,
    C = factorC
  )
head(Wheat_groups)

Wheat_groups <- Wheatgroups %>%
  mutate(
    gA = case_when(
      A == "A2" ~ "A2",
      A == "A4" ~ "A4",
      TRUE ~ "random" ),
    sA = as.numeric(gA == "random"),

    gB = case_when(
      B == "B2" ~ "B2",
      B == "B4" ~ "B4",
      B == "B6" ~ "B6",
      B == "B8" ~ "B8",
      TRUE ~ "random" ),
    sB = as.numeric(gB == "random"),

    gC = case_when(
      C == "C1" ~ "C1",
      C == "C2" ~ "C2",
      C == "C3" ~ "C3",
      TRUE ~ "random" ),
    sC = as.numeric(gC == "random")
  )
head(Wheat_groups)

## Fool-proof derivation of all effects of the three-way model
```

```

# Each effect is formed by "termA.termB.termC".
# The first term corresponds to general intercept and can be
ignored,
# as this term is fitted by default

# Define the values for each term
termA_values <- c("", "gA", "gA.A.sA")
termB_values <- c("", "gB", "gB.B.sB")
termC_values <- c("", "gC", "gC.C.sC")

# Create all combinations (Cartesian product)
effects <- expand.grid(
  termA = termA_values,
  termB = termB_values,
  termC = termC_values,
  stringsAsFactors = FALSE
)

# Print the resulting data frame
print(effects)

# Fit the mixed-effects model

model <- lmer(
  Yield ~ gA * gB * gC + # fixed effects
  (1|rep:A)+ # Random effects
  (1|rep:A:B)+
  (sA-1 | gA:A) +
  (sA-1 | gA:A:gB) +
  (sB-1 | gB:B) +
  (sB-1 | gA:gB:B) +
  (sA:sB-1 | gA:A:gB:B) +
  (sA-1 | gA:A:gC) +
  (sA-1 | gA:A:gB:gC) +
  (sB-1 | gB:B:gC) +
  (sB-1 | gA:gB:B:gC) +
  (sA:sB-1 | gA:A:gB:B:gC) +
  (sC-1 | gC:C) +
  (sC-1|gA:gC:C)+
  (sA:sC-1 | gA:A:gC:C) +
  (sC-1 | gB:gC:C) +
  (sC-1 | gA:gB:gC:C) +
  (sA:sC-1 | gA:A:gB:gC:C) +
  (sB:sC-1 | gB:B:gC:C)+
  (sB:sC-1 | gA:gB:B:gC:C)+
  (sA:sB:sC-1 | gA:A:gB:B:gC:C),
  data = wheat_groups)
summary(model, ddf="Kenward-Roger")

```

Supplementary Box 12(a): SAS PROC GLIMMIX code for mean comparison using SLICE or %MULT macro for the reduced split-split-plot model.

```

** First submit/run the %mult code here once **;

/*The Wheat Example - SLICE with GLIMMIX */
/* Random effects removed:  rep(A), rep(A*B), gA*gC*C*sC */

proc glimmix data=Wheat_groups ;
class A B C gA gB gC rep ;
model yield= gA|gB|gC / ddfm=kr solution;
random gA*A*sA
      gA*A*sA*gB
      gB*B*sB
      gA*gB*B*sB
      gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB
      gA*A*sA*gC
      gA*A*sA*gB*gC
      gB*B*sB*gC
      gA*gB*B*sB*gC
      gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB*gC
      gC*C*sC
      gA*A*sA*gC*C*sC
      gB*gC*C*sC
      gA*gB*gC*C*sC
      gA*A*sA*gB*gC*C*sC
      gB*B*sB*gC*C*sC
      gA*gB*B*sB*gC*C*sC
      gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB*gC*C*sC;
covtest / wald;
slice gA*gB*gC/sliceby=gA*gC lines;
run;

/*The Wheat Example - %MULT with GLIMMIX */
proc glimmix data=Wheat_groups ;
ods output lsmeans=lsmeans diffs=diffs;
class A B C gA gB gC rep ;
model yield= gA|gB|gC / ddfm=kr solution;
random gA*A*sA
      gA*A*sA*gB
      gB*B*sB
      gA*gB*B*sB
      gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB
      gA*A*sA*gC
      gA*A*sA*gB*gC
      gB*B*sB*gC
      gA*gB*B*sB*gC
      gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB*gC

```

```

gC*C*sC
gA*A*sA*gC*C*sC
gB*gC*C*sC
gA*gB*gC*C*sC
gA*A*sA*gB*gC*C*sC
gB*B*sB*gC*C*sC
gA*gB*B*sB*gC*C*sC
gA*A*sA*gB*B*sB*gC*C*sC;
covtest / wald;
lsmeans gA*gB*gC/pdiff;
%mult(trt=gB, by=gA, by2=gC);
run;
Title "LS-means for the Split-split-plot Reduced Model ";
run;

```

Supplementary Box 12(b): R code for slicing and mean comparison for the reduced split-split-plot model.

```

# Load required packages
library(lme4)          # Linear mixed models
library(lmerTest)     # Kenward-Roger/Satterthwaite df
library(emmeans)     # LS-means
library(multcomp)     # cld() for emmeans
library(multcompView) # Optional low-level CLDs
library(ggplot2)     # Plotting
library(dplyr)       # Data handling

# Fit the reduced mixed-effects model

# Random effects with zero variances removed:  rep:A, rep:A:B,
gA:gC:C:sC

model <- lmer(
  Yield ~ gA * gB * gC + # fixed effects
  (sA-1 | gA:A) + # Random effects
  (sA-1 | gA:A:gB) +
  (sB-1 | gB:B) +
  (sB-1 | gA:gB:B) +
  (sA:sB-1 | gA:A:gB:B) +
  (sA-1 | gA:A:gC) +
  (sA-1 | gA:A:gB:gC) +
  (sB-1 | gB:B:gC) +
  (sB-1 | gA:gB:B:gC) +
  (sA:sB-1 | gA:A:gB:B:gC) +
  (sC-1 | gC:C) +
  (sA:sC-1 | gA:A:gC:C) +
  (sC-1 | gB:gC:C) +
  (sC-1 | gA:gB:gC:C) +

```

```

(sA:sC-1 | gA:A:gB:gC:C) +
(sB:sC-1 | gB:B:gC:C)+
(sB:sC-1 | gA:gB:B:gC:C)+
(sA:sB:sC-1 | gA:A:gB:B:gC:C),
data = Wheat_groups)

summary(model, ddf="Kenward-Roger")

# -----
### Generate marginal means of gB sliced by groupAxgroupC
# -----

emmeans_results <- emmeans(model, ~ gB|gA*gC)

## Pairwise comparisons within each slice (Unadjusted -t-tests)
pairwise_results <- contrast(emmeans_results, method = "pairwise",
adjust = "none")

## Display pairwise results
print(pairwise_results)

# -----
### Generate compact Letter Display (Unadjusted t-tests for p-
values)
# -----
cld_results <- cld(emmeans_results, adjust = "none", Letters =
letters)
print(cld_results)

# -----
### Plot: LS-means with Letters
# -----

# Ensure gA and gC are factors (required for interaction below)
cld_results$gA <- as.factor(cld_results$gA)
cld_results$gC <- as.factor(cld_results$gC)
cld_results$gB <- as.factor(cld_results$gB)

# Create interaction factor
cld_results$gA_gC <- interaction(cld_results$gA, cld_results$gC)

# Plot
ggplot(cld_results, aes(x = gB, y = emmean, color = gA_gC)) +
  geom_point(position = position_dodge(width = 0.5), size = 3) +
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = emmean - SE, ymax = emmean + SE),

```

```

width = 0.2, position = position_dodge(width =
0.5)) +
  geom_text(aes(label = .group),
            position = position_dodge(width = 0.5), vjust = -1.2,
size = 5) +
  labs(
    title = "LS-means of gB sliced by gA × gC (Letter Display)",
    x = "gB", y = "Estimated Marginal Mean"
  ) +
  theme_minimal(base_size = 14)

# -----
### Generate SED, LSD, and HSD for gB when gA = "random" and gC =
"C1"
# -----
# Summary Table of SED, LSD, and HSD for gB
# When gA = "random" and gC = "C1"
# -----

library(tibble)

# Step 1: Get emmeans for gB at gA = "random" and gC = "C1"
emm_slice <- emmeans(model, ~ gB,
                    at = list(gA = "random", gC = "C1"))

# Step 2: Pairwise contrasts of gB
pairwise <- contrast(emm_slice, method = "pairwise")

# Step 3: Extract values for LSD (no adjustment)
lsd_summary <- summary(pairwise, adjust = "none") %>%
  as.data.frame()

# Step 4: Extract values for HSD (no adjustment)
hsd_summary <- summary(pairwise, adjust = "none") %>%
  as.data.frame()

# Step 5: Build summary table
summary_table <- tibble(
  Variable = c("SED", "LSD", "HSD"),
  Minimum = c(min(lsd_summary$SE),
              min(abs(lsd_summary$estimate)),
              min(abs(hsd_summary$estimate))),
  Mean = c(mean(lsd_summary$SE),
           mean(abs(lsd_summary$estimate)),
           mean(abs(hsd_summary$estimate))),
  Maximum = c(max(lsd_summary$SE),
              max(abs(lsd_summary$estimate)),
              max(abs(hsd_summary$estimate)))
)

```

```
# Step 6: Print the summary table
print(summary_table, digits = 7)
```

Supplementary Tables

The single-factor analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the Bute on-farm trials data (Trengove et al. 2023) reported in the Trengove Consulting and GRDC projects DAS 905-011RTX and TGC2304-002RTX.

Supplementary Table 1: ANOVA for Lime Product (factor A)

	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-value	P-value
Product	5	0.544	0.1087	0.923	0.481
Residuals	27	3.180	0.1178		
Treatment means					
Angaston	Control	Kulpara	Spalding	Sulphur	Venning
5.8984	5.5528	5.7791	5.6718	5.5516	5.8231
Grand Mean	5.7270				

Supplementary Table 2: ANOVA for Lime Incorporation Method (Factor B)

	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-value	P-value	
Incorporation	6	0.2623	0.0437	1.17	0.344	
Residuals	35	1.3075	0.0374			
Treatment means						
Deep-rip	Inc-rip	No-til	Offset-disc	Offset-inc	Offset-inc-spade	Spade
5.6967	5.8067	5.8833	5.8767	5.8983	5.8967	5.7233
Grand Mean	5.8260					

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure 1: Simulation algorithm for a two-factor experiment

Note: Data simulation process: $\hat{Y}_{ij} = \mu_c^{(e)} + \alpha_i^{(f)} + \beta_j^{(g)} + (\alpha\beta)_{ij}^{(p)} + \varepsilon_{ijk}^{(k)}$.

The superscripts (e), (f), (g), (p) and (k) in the formula are the simulation stages in Supplementary Figure 1. The three-factor experiment will have additional routes for factor C, that are similar to (a)-(f) and (a)-(l)-(n), that will converge at (n); (b)-(e) and (h)-(j) that will converge at (e) and (j), respectively. Data simulation process depends on the experimental design in question.

Supplementary Notes

Supplementary Note 1: Parameters for data simulation for the two-factor experiment

One-way analyses of variance were performed for each of the two factors (A and B) to obtain treatment means ($\bar{X}^{(A)}$ and $\bar{X}^{(B)}$), treatment effects ($\tau_i^{(A)}$ and $\tau_j^{(B)}$) and error variances (σ_A^2 and σ_B^2). For each factor, the overall mean ($\bar{X}_{..}$) was estimated and used to estimate the treatment effects as:

$$\tau_i^{(A)} = \bar{X}_i^{(A)} - \bar{X}_{..}^{(A)}$$

The two overall means and error variances were again averaged to get the grand mean (μ_c) and combined variance, that were used to simulate data for the two-factor experiment and the error term as, respectively:

$$\hat{\mu}_c = \frac{1}{2}(\bar{X}_{..}^{(A)} + \bar{X}_{..}^{(B)})$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_c^2 = \frac{1}{2}(\hat{\sigma}_A^2 + \hat{\sigma}_B^2)$$

Interactions between the two factors were simulated from a normal distribution with mean zero and constant variance, where the variance is estimated as the average of the variance of the treatment means in each of the two experiments as:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{pooled}^2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\hat{\sigma}_{\bar{X}_i^{(A)}}^2 + \hat{\sigma}_{\bar{X}_j^{(B)}}^2 \right)$$

i.e., the interaction effects follow the normal distribution, $N(0, \hat{\sigma}_{pooled}^2)$.

Supplementary Note 2: R code for simulating data for a two-factor experiment

The following procedure (R code) was used to simulate data for the two-factor experiment, where factor A has 6 levels, and factor B has 7 levels, with 5 replications per treatment. The model parameters were obtained from the Bute on-farm trials, 2022 barley data (see Supplementary Tables 1 and 2), from the Trengove Consulting and GRDC projects (DAS 905-011RTX and TGC2304-002RTX).

```
# Define the levels for each factor
FactorA_levels <- c("A1", "A2", "A3", "A4", "A5", "A6")
FactorB_levels <- c("B1", "B2", "B3", "B4", "B5", "B6", "B7")
Replications <- 5

# Generate the data frame
simulated_data <- data.frame(
  FactorA = rep(rep(FactorA_levels, each = Replications), times = length(FactorB_levels)),
```

```

FactorB = rep(FactorB_levels, each = length(FactorA_levels) * Replications),
Rep = rep(1:Replications, times = length(FactorA_levels) * length(FactorB_levels))
)

# Treatment means for factor A
alpha_means <- c(5.8984, 5.5528, 5.7791, 5.6718, 5.5516, 5.8231)
grand_meanA <- 5.7270
alpha_effects <- alpha_means - grand_meanA

# Treatment means for factor B
beta_means <- c(5.7233, 5.6967, 5.8767, 5.8833, 5.8067, 5.8983, 5.8967)
grand_meanB <- 5.8260
beta_effects <- beta_means - grand_meanB

# Pooled Variance of treatment error
var_trtA <- var(alpha_means)
var_trtB <- var(beta_means)
pooled_trt_sd <- sqrt(0.5 * (var_trtA + var_trtB))

# Overall Mean and Variance of error
var_A <- 0.1178 # from one-way ANOVA for factor A
var_B <- 0.0374 # from one-way ANOVA for factor B

overall_sd <- sqrt(0.5 * (var_A + var_B))
overall_mean <- 0.5 * (grand_meanA + grand_meanB)

# Generate interaction effects
set.seed(123) # For reproducibility
alpha_beta_effects <- rnorm( length(FactorA_levels) * length(FactorB_levels),
  mean = 0, sd = pooled_trt_sd)

# Simulate the error term (normally distributed random errors)
error_term <- rnorm(
  nrow(simulated_data),
  mean = 0,
  sd = overall_sd
)

# Generate the response (yield) column
simulated_data$yield <- with(simulated_data, {
  alpha_effect <- alpha_effects[match(FactorA, FactorA_levels)]
  beta_effect <- beta_effects[match(FactorB, FactorB_levels)]
  interaction_effect <- alpha_beta_effects[
    (match(FactorA, FactorA_levels) - 1) * length(FactorB_levels) +
    match(FactorB, FactorB_levels)
  ]
  overall_mean + alpha_effect + beta_effect + interaction_effect + error_term
})
head(simulated_data) # View the simulated data

```

Supplementary Note 3: R code for simulating data for the repeated-measures experiment

The following R code was used to simulate data for the three-factor repeated-measures experiment, with two between-subjects factors: factor A with 6 levels, and factor B with 7 levels, observed on 4 consecutive times (Time) with 6 replications per treatment on a single response variable (NDVI). The model parameters were obtained from the Bute on-farm trials (Trengove Consulting and GRDC projects (DAS 905-011RTX and TGC2304-002RTX)).

```
set.seed(123) # for reproducibility

# Define levels
FactorA_levels <- c("A1", "A2", "A3", "A4", "A5", "A6")
FactorB_levels <- c("B1", "B2", "B3", "B4", "B5", "B6", "B7")
Time_levels <- 1:4
Replications <- 6
rho <- 0.7 # AR(1) autocorrelation

# Create the full data frame
NDVIdata2 <- data.frame(
  FactorA = rep(FactorA_levels, each = length(FactorB_levels) * length(Time_levels) *
  Replications),
  FactorB = rep(rep(FactorB_levels, each = length(Time_levels) * Replications), times =
  length(FactorA_levels)),
  Time = rep(rep(Time_levels, each = Replications), times = length(FactorA_levels) *
  length(FactorB_levels)),
  Rep = rep(1:Replications, times = length(FactorA_levels) * length(FactorB_levels) *
  length(Time_levels))
)

## Simulation parameters
# Treatment means for factor A
alpha_means <- c(0.7416, 0.8670, 0.7707, 0.6615,
  0.7279, 0.8670, 0.7727, 0.6620,
  0.7176, 0.8583, 0.7749, 0.6207,
  0.7446, 0.8640, 0.7856, 0.6394,
  0.7086, 0.8661, 0.7928, 0.6670,
  0.7253, 0.8685, 0.7787, 0.6376)
grand_meanA <- mean(alpha_means)
alpha_effects <- alpha_means - grand_meanA

# Treatment means for factor B
beta_means <- c(0.5765, 0.8600, 0.7432, 0.6572,
  0.5926, 0.8638, 0.7792, 0.6661,
  0.7146, 0.8542, 0.6880, 0.6007,
  0.7519, 0.8676, 0.8005, 0.6800,
  0.6961, 0.8619, 0.6945, 0.5633,
```

```

0.7363, 0.8751, 0.8248, 0.7434,
0.7760, 0.8667, 0.8210, 0.7119)
grand_meanB <- mean(beta_means)
beta_effects <- beta_means - grand_meanB

# Treatment means for Time
gamma_means <- c(0.7107, 0.8646, 0.7712, 0.6533)
grand_meanTime <- mean(gamma_means)
gamma_effects <- gamma_means - grand_meanTime

# Variance and error SD
var_A <- var(alpha_means); var_B <- var(beta_means); var_Time <- var(gamma_means)
pooled_sd <- sqrt(0.5 * (var_A + var_B + var_Time))
overall_mean <- (grand_meanA + grand_meanB + grand_meanTime) / 3

# Simulate interaction effects
set.seed(123)
alpha_beta_effects <- rnorm(length(FactorA_levels) * length(FactorB_levels), mean = 0, sd =
pooled_sd)
alpha_gamma_effects <- rnorm(length(FactorA_levels) * length(Time_levels), mean = 0, sd =
pooled_sd)
beta_gamma_effects <- rnorm(length(FactorB_levels) * length(Time_levels), mean = 0, sd =
pooled_sd)
alpha_beta_gamma_effects <- rnorm(length(FactorA_levels) * length(FactorB_levels) *
length(Time_levels), mean = 0, sd = pooled_sd)

# Generate AR(1) errors for each replicate
library(dplyr)
NDVIdata2 <- NDVIdata %>% arrange(FactorA, FactorB, Rep, Time)
NDVIdata2$AR_error <- NA

unique_units <- unique(NDVIdata[, c("FactorA", "FactorB", "Rep")])

for (i in 1:nrow(unique_units)) {
  this_unit <- unique_units[i, ]
  idx <- with(NDVIdata, FactorA == this_unit$FactorA & FactorB == this_unit$FactorB & Rep
== this_unit$Rep)

  # Simulate AR(1) error
  e <- numeric(length(Time_levels))
  e[1] <- rnorm(1, mean = 0, sd = pooled_sd)
  for (t in 2:length(Time_levels)) {
    e[t] <- rho * e[t - 1] + sqrt(1 - rho^2) * rnorm(1, mean = 0, sd = pooled_sd)
  }
  NDVIdata2$AR_error[idx] <- e
}

```

```

# Generate responses with AR(1) errors
NDVIdata2$NDVI <- with(NDVIdata, {
  alpha_effect <- alpha_effects[match(FactorA, FactorA_levels)]
  beta_effect <- beta_effects[match(FactorB, FactorB_levels)]
  gamma_effect <- gamma_effects[Time]

  alpha_beta <- alpha_beta_effects[(match(FactorA, FactorA_levels) - 1) *
length(FactorB_levels) + match(FactorB, FactorB_levels)]
  alpha_gamma <- alpha_gamma_effects[(match(FactorA, FactorA_levels) - 1) *
length(Time_levels) + Time]
  beta_gamma <- beta_gamma_effects[(match(FactorB, FactorB_levels) - 1) *
length(Time_levels) + Time]
  alpha_beta_gamma <- alpha_beta_gamma_effects[
  (match(FactorA, FactorA_levels) - 1) * length(FactorB_levels) * length(Time_levels) +
  (match(FactorB, FactorB_levels) - 1) * length(Time_levels) +
  Time]

  raw_response <- overall_mean + alpha_effect + beta_effect + gamma_effect +
  alpha_beta + alpha_gamma + beta_gamma + alpha_beta_gamma + AR_error

  pmax(0, pmin(raw_response, 0.9999))
})

# View a sample
head(NDVIdata2, 10)

write.csv(NDVIdata2, "Bute.NDVIdata2.csv", row.names = FALSE)
getwd()

```

Supplementary Note 4: R code for simulating data for the split-split-plot experiment

The following procedure (R code) was used to simulate data for the split-split-plot experiment, where the whole-plot factor A has 5 levels, and split-plot factor B has 8 levels, the split-split-plot factor C has 6 levels, with 3 replications per treatment. The model parameters were obtained from various on-farm wheat irrigation trials.

```

# Define the factors
# Libraries
library(stats)

# Define the factors
factorA <- c("A1", "A2", "A3", "A4", "A5") # Whole-plot factor
factorB <- c("B1", "B2", "B3", "B4", "B5", "B6", "B7", "B8") # Split-plot factor
factorC <- c("C1", "C2", "C3", "C4", "C5", "C6") # Split-split-plot factor

```

```

# Number of replicates
n_replicates <- 3

# Define treatment means and effects as before
alpha_means <- c(6.4792, 6.801, 8.22, 5.8867, 6.2408)
grand_meanA <- 6.7255
alpha_effects <- alpha_means - grand_meanA

beta_means <- c(6.565, 6.205, 6.45, 6.015, 5.845, 5.455, 4.66, 4.6)
grand_meanB <- 5.724375
beta_effects <- beta_means - grand_meanB

gamma_means <- c(7.5550, 7.0575, 7.6000, 7.5125, 7.9325, 7.9525)
grand_meanC <- 7.5775
gamma_effects <- gamma_means - grand_meanC

# Variance and error settings
var_beta <- var(beta_means)
var_alpha <- var(alpha_means)
var_gamma <- var(gamma_means)
pooled_trt_sd <- sqrt((var_alpha + var_beta + var_gamma) / 3)
overall_sd <- mean(c(0.8998, 0.7590, 1.232))
overall_mean <- mean(c(grand_meanA, grand_meanB, grand_meanC))

# Interaction effects
set.seed(123)
alpha.beta_effects <- rnorm(length(factorA) * length(factorB), mean = 0, sd = pooled_trt_sd)
alpha.gamma_effects <- rnorm(length(factorA) * length(factorC), mean = 0, sd =
pooled_trt_sd)
beta.gamma_effects <- rnorm(length(factorB) * length(factorC), mean = 0, sd =
pooled_trt_sd)
alpha.beta.gamma_effects <- rnorm(length(factorA) * length(factorB) * length(factorC),
mean = 0, sd = pooled_trt_sd)

# Generate design matrix for split-split-plot
design <- expand.grid(
  factorC = factorC,
  factorB = factorB,
  factorA = factorA)

# Ensure hierarchical nesting
design <- design[order(design$factorA, design$factorB, design$factorC), ]

# Simulate response data
responses <- numeric(nrow(design) * n_replicates)
counter <- 1
error_term <- rnorm(length(responses), mean = 0, sd = overall_sd)

```

```

for (i in 1:nrow(design)) {
  for (j in 1:n_replicates) {
    treatment_effect <- overall_mean +
      alpha_effects[as.numeric(design$factorA[i])] +
      beta_effects[as.numeric(design$factorB[i])] +
      gamma_effects[as.numeric(design$factorC[i])] +
      alpha.beta_effects[(as.numeric(design$factorA[i]) - 1) * length(factorB) +
as.numeric(design$factorB[i])] +
      alpha.gamma_effects[(as.numeric(design$factorA[i]) - 1) * length(factorC) +
as.numeric(design$factorC[i])] +
      beta.gamma_effects[(as.numeric(design$factorB[i]) - 1) * length(factorC) +
as.numeric(design$factorC[i])] +
      alpha.beta.gamma_effects[(as.numeric(design$factorA[i]) - 1) * length(factorB) *
length(factorC) +
      (as.numeric(design$factorB[i]) - 1) * length(factorC) +
      as.numeric(design$factorC[i])]

    responses[counter] <- treatment_effect + error_term[counter]
    counter <- counter + 1
  }
}

# Create simulated data frame
Wheatdata <- data.frame(
  factorA = rep(design$factorA, each = n_replicates),
  factorB = rep(design$factorB, each = n_replicates),
  factorC = rep(design$factorC, each = n_replicates),
  rep = rep(1:n_replicates, times = nrow(design)),
  Yield = responses
)

# View the first few rows
head(Wheatdata)

```